

FACULTY PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT ON INSTRUCTIONAL PRACTICES: BASIS FOR TEACHING PEDAGOGY

Leovigildo Lito D. Mallillin¹, Wenald H. Lopez²

^{1,2*}University of Calocan City

Corresponding Email: 1lovie_mallillin@getinternational.org

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Abstract:

The research study aims to identify and explore the faculty professional development on instructional practices as a basis for teaching pedagogy. Mixed methods are the research designed utilized in the study from the result of triangulation that deals with Focus Group Discussion (FGD). Hence, purposive sampling technique is used in the sample population process. It is used based on the pre-defined criteria of the research process. The study composed One Hundred Seventy-Five (175) respondents only. Results indicate that faculty development on instructional practices for teaching pedagogy among the respondents express expertise success of development in teaching through student learning and evaluation, show that individual skills on teaching pedagogy provides individual skills to develop, lead, initiate, and plan for the subject area of student learning, show that knowledge on teaching pedagogy provides an insight for student to learn differently in various topics and lessons to be conducted in the learning process, show that expertise on teaching pedagogy helps for teaching the subject didactics and learning inside the classroom, and show that characteristics of a faculty focuses on the various instructional practices and teaching pedagogy as to order of thinking skills, psychological approach to learning, and educational principles in teaching and practices. Findings indicate that there is a significant relationship on the faculty professional development on instructional practices as a basis for teaching pedagogy by the participants.

Keywords: Faculty professional development, teaching pedagogy, individual skills, knowledge, expertise, and characteristics of a faculty

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INTRODUCTION

Professional development on instructional practices is necessary in teaching pedagogy. It recognizes the activities defined for teaching pedagogies such as characteristics of a faculty, expertise, knowledge, and individual skills. It develops a high quality instruction for faculty in a positive effect to the learners. It improves the faculty professional development on instructional practice in every classroom. It increases varied faculty instructional practices. It explores facilitating positive learning participation in the classroom. It explores active teaching and learning through instructional practices and concepts. It addresses the concept to uphold teaching and learning through proper active teaching techniques and strategies. It helps to engage improvement in the performance of students. Lack of time, motivation, incentives, and professional development are impediment opportunities for creating instructional materials. It provides various skills and approaches in the educational system and teaching pedagogy as to acquiring knowledge, reflection, effectiveness, implementation, requirements, and standard skills for instructional practices (Mallillin, & Laurel, 2022). It examines the faculty instructional practices in teaching pedagogy for various educational institutions. This includes training gaps and issues, development of teaching pedagogy, updates on training professional development, school culture, productivity, and skills. It improves faculty development and professional program outcome and assessment such as faculty success and perspectives, institutional, and organizational culture development of respect and trust, expectation, understanding and aspect of roles on faculty professional development on instructional practices in teaching pedagogy (Mallillin, 2023).

On the other hand, involving faculty challenges may overcome the opportunity for professional development. It is an iterative design to be utilized in active learning and teaching pedagogy. It is focused on the central dogma of learning and concept difficulties related to professional development on instructional practice. It explores the efficacy of learning to protect and motivate faculty change from good, better, and best as part of professional development on instructional practices in teaching and learning. It collaborates faculty involvement on professional development instructional practice approach for learning positively on the effect of students' understanding teaching pedagogy. It influences the involvement process of faculty professional development and willingness for new instructional practices. It is a based design approach in teaching pedagogy for student learning. The challenges involve the performance of the faculty in terms of competency level and skills that need to be developed for professional development in terms of instructional practices. Faculties are innovators for shaping and molding the minds of the learners. It examines professional development and competency skills and levels to the fullest (Mallillin, & Mallillin, 2019). On the other hand, faculty professional development on instructional practices in teaching pedagogy examines intervention implementation teaching as molders of students. It explores the various professional development of faculties. It identifies the function of teacher model theory for professional development in adapting intervention for faculties as resourceful, effective, honest, creativity, adaptability, enthusiastic, and talent (Mallillin, 2022, pp. 99-121).

Furthermore, the design for faculty professional development on instructional practices in the teaching pedagogy models the lecturers for active learning. The design for the instructional practices in teaching pedagogy is a model to be utilized in assessment, active learning, and scientific teaching and learning to include inclusive teaching for immersive professional development. It is an instructional practice in teaching pedagogy to be utilized. It increases active learning for faculties among students inside the classroom setting. It draws inspiration among faculty engagement. It is a practice pedagogy for faculty professional development on instructional practice and belief. It

provides a reflection for faculty professional development in teaching pedagogy and instructional practices. It provides an opportunity to implement and discuss development of faculty advancement. It supports faculty professional development on instructional practice and experiences. The design for the faculty professional development contributes to efficient classroom pedagogy and instructional practice that can lead to effective teaching management. It provides a better effective learning process. This involves instructional practices and teaching pedagogy. It leads to a better learning outcome for the academic performance of students based on the faculty professional development such as knowledge of the lesson, analyzing inferences, formation, and critical thinking. The design provides instructional practice in effective teaching pedagogy to various learning processes (Mallillin, et al. 2023, pp. 41-52). In addition, the design of faculty professional development on instructional practice to teaching pedagogy assesses facilitation of teaching and learning in teaching development management, teaching trends, and skills productivity. It focuses on proper planning and success of instructional practice in teaching pedagogy based on faculty professional development (Mallillin, 2023, pp. 12-28).

Indeed, the purpose of faculty professional development provides the process of coaching and training among the lecturers to help improve the performance pedagogy process. It focuses on the program in enhancing classroom delivery. It emerges as an initiative on the needs and process of faculty development instructional practices in teaching pedagogy. It involves teaching strategy towards students' learning and development. This is one of the global standards in the Commission of Higher Education Institutions. It is a program that provides rebranding in the different educational institutions to be planned in accordance to faculty professional development on instructional practices and teaching pedagogy. It enhances programs for the academic and intellectual environment of the various educational institutions by providing faculty the proper professional development through workshops, conferences, and seminar participation. This can update teaching pedagogy skills among faculties. It examines effectiveness and faculty perception of professional development on instructional practice and teaching pedagogy (Vela, et al. 2023). Finally, the purpose of faculty professional development is to provide proper training in enhancing the skills in teaching and learning. It guides effective management of educational mechanisms and systems (Mallillin, 2022). It is crucial in the educational system. It provides success in the educational institutions. It provides proper training and professional development. It engages on the faculty development activities to their profession as faculties in the educational institution. It describes program and development of faculties in teaching pedagogy (Luthra, et al. 2023).

Statement of the Problem

1. What is the faculty professional development on instructional practices as a basis for teaching pedagogy among the respondents?
2. How may the faculty development on instructional practices become the basis for teaching pedagogy?
3. Is there a significant agreement on the faculty professional development on instructional practices as a basis for teaching pedagogy as observed by the respondents?

Hypothesis

There is a significant agreement on the faculty professional development on instructional practices as a basis for teaching pedagogy as observed by the participants.

Research Design

Mixed methods are the designs utilized in the research process. It deals with both quantitative and qualitative research which is a result of triangulation or Focus Group Discussion (FGD). Quantitative research design focuses on measuring and quantifying the faculty professional development on instructional practices of the respondents in the area of individual skills, knowledge, expertise, and characteristics of a faculty. Hence, qualitative research design is focusing on evaluating the faculty development on instructional practices as basis for teaching pedagogy which is the result of Focus Group Discussion (FGD) through themes and analysis of the study. Mixed methods are suitable in the research problem for measuring the faculty professional development on instructional practices in teaching pedagogy. It addresses the concept, gaps, framework, and guidance (Younas, et al. 2023).

Sampling Techniques

Purposive sampling technique is employed in the selection of the population size. It is used based on the pre-defined criteria. It refers to the non-probability sampling techniques and characteristics needed for the sampling method and process. It identifies the process and insights in the selection of the population size of the research. It contributes for faculty development on instructional practices in teaching pedagogy for analysis. It is a tool to describe the process of purposive sampling technique for the research process. It is an approach used to provide a wide range in the selection of sample size which is vital in the collection process of the sample data involved. It addresses and identifies the utilization of the data used for sampling techniques (Thomas, 2022, pp. 1-8).

Subjects of the Study

The subjects of the research study are the faculties of the different school institutions at the Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) for both public and private colleges and universities in Metro Manila. The participants are chosen based on the pre-defined criteria that the respondents must be faculty of both public and private universities or colleges. They have been teaching for at least 3 years and above. They are exposed to teaching pedagogy for various techniques and trends in teaching strategies. They are using various instructional materials in teaching. The instructional materials must be based on the trends of teaching strategies. The study composed One Hundred Seventy-Five (175) participants only.

RESULTS

1. What is the faculty professional development on instructional practices of the respondents as basis for teaching pedagogy in the area of individual skills, knowledge, expertise, and characteristics of a faculty?

Table 1

Faculty Professional Development on Instructional Practices as Basis for Teaching Pedagogy

Indicators	WM	I	R
1. It plays an important role in teaching pedagogy to help and understand the best way to provide instructional materials inside the classroom.	4.09	A	4.5
2. It provides a pedagogical teaching practice expertise in the subject interest learning of students.	3.71	A	10
3. It acts through discovery in teaching pedagogy methods and concepts for technological advancement in learning.	4.00	A	6.5
4. It provides individual skills to develop, lead, initiate, and plan for the subject area of student learning.	3.97	A	8

5. It expresses expertise in the success of development in teaching through student learning and evaluation.	4.21	SA	1.5
6. It provides an insight for students to learn differently in various topics and lessons to be conducted in the learning process.	3.38	MA	11.5
7. It drives for a desired output in teaching pedagogy and instructional practice output method.	3.88	A	9
8. It connects capacity for the course program or subject modules to be taught as part of the learning process.	4.09	A	4.5
9. It helps for pedagogical expertise and interaction for teaching the subject didactics and learning inside the classroom.	4.00	A	6.5
10. It focuses on the various characteristics of instructional practices and teaching pedagogy such as order of thinking skills, psychological approach to learning, and educational principles in teaching and practices.	3.38	MA	11.5
11. It helps in the improved instructional practices and teaching pedagogy to provide quality education.	4.21	SA	1.5
12. It reflects the individual skills for teaching and learning development for the critical thinking approach process.	4.17	A	3
Average Weighted Mean	3.92	A	
Standard Deviation	0.291		

Table 1 presents the weighted mean and the corresponding interpretation on the faculty development on instructional practices as basis for teaching pedagogy among the respondents.

It indicates that rank 1 is shared by the two indicators which are "It expresses expertise in the success of development in teaching through student learning and evaluation", and "It helps in the improved instructional practices and teaching pedagogy to provide quality education", with a weighted mean of 4.21 or Strongly Agree which means instructional practices on teaching pedagogy is highly observed. Rank 2 is "It reflects the individual skills for teaching and learning development for critical thinking approach process", with a weighted mean of 4.17 or Agree which means instructional practices on teaching pedagogy is observed. Rank 3 is also shared by the two indicators which are "It plays an important role in teaching pedagogy to help and understand the best way to provide instructional materials inside the classroom", and "It connects capacity for the course program or subject modules to be taught inside the classroom", with a weighted mean of 4.09 or Agree which means instructional practices on teaching pedagogy is observed. The least in rank is shared by the two indicators which are "It provides an insight for student to learn differently in various topics and lessons to be conducted in the learning process", and "It focuses on the various characteristics of instructional practices and teaching pedagogy as to order of thinking skills, psychological approach to learning, and educational principles in teaching and practices", with a weighted mean of 3.30 or Moderately Agree which means instructional practices on teaching pedagogy is limited. The overall average weighted mean is 3.92 (SD=0.291) or Agree which means faculty development on instructional practices among the participants is observed.

Findings show that faculty professional development provides the process of coaching and training among the lecturers to help improve performance pedagogy in learning. It explores objectives in enhancing classroom delivery. It emerges from the initiative needs and process of faculty development instructional practices in teaching pedagogy. It involves teaching strategy towards students' learning and development. This is one of the global standards in the Commission of Higher Education Institutions. It is a program that provides rebranding in the different educational institutions to be planned in accordance to faculty professional development on instructional practices and teaching pedagogy. It enhances the academic and intellectual environment of various educational institutions by providing

faculty the proper professional development through workshops, conferences, and seminar participation. This can update teaching pedagogy skills among faculties. It examines effectiveness and faculty perception of professional development instructional practice and teaching pedagogy (Vela, et al. 2023).

2. How may the faculty development on instructional practices become the basis for teaching pedagogy?

Presented in this table are the themes, response of the respondents, and the core ideas on faculty professional development on instructional practices as basis for teaching pedagogy. The response of the respondents is categorized as follows: 5.00-4.20=Strongly Agree, 4.19-3.40=Agree. 3.39-2.60, Moderately Agree, 2.59-1.80=Disagree, and 1.79-1.00=Strongly Disagree. Verbatim text is also provided for theme analysis.

Table 2

Thematic Analysis on the Instructional Practices as Basis for Teaching Pedagogy

Themes	Response of the Respondents	Core Ideas
1. Individual Skills on Teaching Pedagogy	Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • student learning • capacity of students • critical thinking
2. Knowledge on Teaching Pedagogy	Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • instructional materials • student learning process • quality education
3. Expertise on Teaching Pedagogy	Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • student academic achievement • student learning evaluation • interaction of teaching
4. Characteristics of a Faculty	Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • educational principles in teaching • concept of learning. • desired teaching output

1. Individual Skills on Teaching Pedagogy

Individual skills in teaching pedagogy refers to the process and techniques given to students during the learning process based on good practices and theory in teaching. It is a relationship strategy in teaching and culture. It aims to explore and build student learning and development skills, behaviors, and attitude. It is predicted on the global approach in learning theory. It connects to the school system to approach teaching and learning in terms of social, cultural, economic, physical, political, and natural instructional practices (Mallillin, 2023). The participants say that:

"It utilizes individual skills to develop, lead, initiate, and plan for the subject area of student learning". T1, P121 & P17

"It connects capacity of learning for the course program or subject modules". T1, P97 & P34

"It reflects individual skills for teaching and learning development critical thinking approach process". T1, P113 & P31

2. Knowledge on Teaching Pedagogy

Pedagogical knowledge in teaching refers to the specialized skills and knowledge for faculties in creating effective and efficient classroom settings to achieve better achievement in the performance of students. It provides the ability to instruct and manage the classroom in a teaching pedagogy setting. It provides knowledge to collaborate for students to understand the teaching and learning to the fullest. Knowledge on teaching pedagogy is a better practice to achieve better performance and achievement in learning. It involves a wide range of knowledge in teaching pedagogy practice methods and practices. It is helpful in teaching pedagogy of faculties on domains of learning (Mallillin, et al. 2021). The participants say that:

"Teaching knowledge plays an important role in teaching pedagogy to help and understand the best way to provide instructional materials inside the classroom". T2, P103 & P54

"It provides an insight for students to learn differently in various topics and lessons to be conducted in the learning process". T2, P131 & P 39

"It helps in the improved instructional practices and teaching pedagogy to provide quality education". T2, P89 & P47

3. Expertise on Teaching Pedagogy

Expertise on teaching pedagogy is based on the knowledge of the different domains to make success in the classroom management and practices. The teaching pedagogy is designed based on the expertise of faculties. This is designed from the different structural domains of learning in setting the parameters of teaching. This can help explore different depth learning activities in teaching. It helps the expert teachers to provide better teaching pedagogy from various domains. When a faculty is expert in teaching pedagogy and classroom management, it means that teaching and learning goes smoothly. It is conducive to learning and has an impact on the academic achievement of learners (Mallillin, 2020, pp. 1-11). The participants say that:

"It explores a pedagogical teaching practice expertise in the subject interest for learning achievement". T3, P100 & P35

"It expresses expertise in the success development of teaching through student learning and evaluation". T3, P120 & P21

"It helps for pedagogical expertise and interaction for teaching the subject didactics and learning inside the classroom". T3, P141 & P16

4. Characteristics of a Faculty

The characteristics of a faculty is necessary as part of professional development on instructional practices in teaching pedagogy. It provides better pedagogical training in teaching which has an impact among faculties for professional vision. It analyzes the characteristics of faculty in teaching pedagogy. It analyzes the attitude and characteristics of faculty as based on professional development on instructional practices in teaching pedagogy perspective in various educational institutions. The characteristics in teaching pedagogy support success and development of the lecturers. It provides success in supporting teaching pedagogy for faculty skills and in-depth profession as molders and shapers of learning (Heinonen, et al. 2023, pp. 201-229). The participants say that:

"It focuses on various characteristics of instructional practices and teaching pedagogy such as order of thinking skills, psychological approach to learning, and educational principles in teaching and practices". T4, P129 & P33

"It acts through discovery in teaching pedagogy methods and concepts for technological advancement in learning". T4, P94 & P63

"It drives for a desired output in teaching pedagogy and instructional practice output in the educational environment". T4, P102 & P47

3. Is there a significant agreement on the faculty professional development on instructional practices as a basis for teaching pedagogy as observed by the respondents?

Table 3

Test of significant agreement on the faculty professional development on instructional practices as basis for teaching pedagogy as observed by the participants

Test of Variables	Computed z value	Interpretation	Decision of Hypothesis
Faculty professional development on instructional practices as basis for teaching pedagogy	96.1299	significant	rejection of the null hypothesis
Two tailed test, at 0.05 level of significant with critical z-value of ± 1.96			

Table 3 presents the test of significant agreement on the faculty professional development on instructional practices as the basis for teaching pedagogy as observed by the respondents.

It indicates in the table that when the variables are tested, it reveals that the z computed value is 96.1299 which reveals significance to the z critical value of ± 1.96, at 0.05 level of significance which resulted in rejection of the null hypothesis. Therefore, it is safe to say that there is a significant agreement on the faculty professional development on instructional practices as a basis for teaching pedagogy as observed by the participants.

Discussion

Faculty development on instructional practices among the respondents show expertise in the success and development of student learning and evaluation. It also shows to help in the improved quality of education. It reflects individual skills for teaching and learning development critical thinking approach processes. It develops a teaching pedagogy in various influences of context and elements in the learning practices. It reflects deeper context and supports pedagogical teaching perspective and development function. It explores context analysis in various teaching pedagogy as to learning structure and practice, norms, principles of teaching, and values. It proposes a support and framework in teaching pedagogy. It promotes and acknowledges teaching development in the school setting (Myllykoski-Laine, et al. 2023, pp. 937-955). In contrast, faculty professional development on instructional practices as a basis for teaching pedagogy shows to play an important role to provide instructional materials inside the classroom. It also shows how to connect capacity for the course program or subject modules. It provides an insight for students to learn differently

in various topics and lessons to be conducted in the learning process. It focuses on the various characteristics of instructional practices and pedagogy such as order of thinking skills, psychological approach to learning, and educational principles in teaching and practices (Fernandes, et al. 2023).

Moreover, individual skills on teaching pedagogy provides individual skills to develop, lead, initiate, and plan for the subject area in learning. It discusses proper professional development in teaching pedagogy that can explore lecturers' techniques, roles, strategies, interaction for teaching and learning, and responsibility of faculty. This includes professional development qualities of a faculty, characteristics, behaviors, beliefs, and mental ability to guide students to the fullest. It is the ability to explore teaching pedagogy through professional development for proper orientation of the school setting to produce quality education toward achievement of the learning and teaching process. It determines the acquired knowledge based on professional development among faculties (Ismailova, 2023, pp. 645-655). On the other hand, individual skills in teaching pedagogy reflect learning development for critical thinking approach processes. It is characterized by the proliferation of information, technological advancement, critical thinking, and fast social change of learning. It is advocated with diverse setting educational goals and objectives in the various educational institutions. It engages with various teaching pedagogy and classroom orientation (Yuan, & Liao, 2023, pp. 543-552). Nonetheless, individual skills in teaching pedagogy show a connected capacity for the course program or subject modules. It develops student competency and qualities in the achievement of academic performance based on the set parameters in teaching pedagogy participation for faculty in the educational institution. It promotes self-competency for learning among faculties. It improves technology competence and advancement to support the role of pedagogical teaching process (Huynh, 2022).

Indeed, knowledge in teaching pedagogy provides an insight for students to learn differently in various topics and lessons to be conducted in the learning process. It aims to expand the knowledge and potential for teaching competency and action of implementation as based on the framework and model of teaching pedagogy techniques for students' academic achievement as part of faculty professional development in the educational institution setting. It draws potential insights in the knowledge of teaching pedagogy models. It is utilized in the teaching pedagogy action and model of competency. It is the best knowledge on competency in teaching pedagogy model strength in teaching (Xing, & Ironsi, 2024). Also, knowledge of teaching pedagogy helps and understands the best way to provide instructional materials inside the classroom. It recognizes the importance and significance of learning as a basis for teaching pedagogy equipped with technology. It is a knowledge designed for instructional materials focused on the various domains of learning and dimensions. It provides phenomena in understanding the knowledge of teaching pedagogy response in different perspectives (Tomita, 2022, pp. 469-502). In addition, knowledge of teaching pedagogy helps in the improved instructional practices to provide quality education. It identifies the topics and subject matters to align with teaching pedagogy and learning. It is the method and approach in teaching pedagogy orientation for learning environment approach, assessment, and support. It is an orientation for teaching pedagogy knowledge and benefits in the school system and process (Gusho, et al. 2023).

Notably, expertise on teaching pedagogy for faculty professional development on instructional practices helps pedagogical expertise and interaction for the subject didactics and learning. It examines the improvement of teaching and expertise for teachers' skills in applying the principles of educational technology and innovation process, decision making, personal characteristics, and pedagogical process. It measures the system process of teaching pedagogy and

development in the educational system. It serves and implements the task of teaching pedagogy to identify the set goals and desired result practice for faculty professional development on instructional practices (Oribjonovich, 2022, pp. 18-22). Hence, expertise in teaching pedagogy expresses the success of development knowledge through student learning and evaluation. It ensures success and key competency of teaching pedagogy development as fundamental priority to quality and learning. It is a fundamental pattern to provide an educational system and expertise in teaching pedagogy skills inside the classroom setting. It focuses on students' skills and teachers' perception to be developed among faculties. It provides better competency initiating teaching and learning, management of self-regulated learning, management information, and management of time for the achievement and accomplishment of the task (García-Toledano, et al. 2023). In addition, expertise in teaching pedagogy provides practice in the subject interest learning output of students. It is a learning culture based on trust, core foundation, growth mindset, and whole reform for student success. It explores the learning culture of student success and school development in terms of justice, respect, and openness in teaching pedagogy expertise (Zhang, 2023, pp. 1-14).

Finally, characteristics of faculty in teaching pedagogy focuses on the various instructional practices as to order of thinking skills, psychological approach to learning, and educational principles and practices. It tends to diffuse instruction and motivation for the psychology domain in education theory based on the characteristics of faculty in the various school settings. It seeks to implement the teaching pedagogy practitioners in a cohesive approach of learning. It explores integration process characteristics of faculty illustrative approach efforts for teaching pedagogy instruction and motivation. It helps in the unification of inter and intra domains of teaching pedagogy engagement (Martin, 2023, pp. 1-35). On the other hand, characteristics of faculty drive for a desired output in teaching pedagogy and instructional practice output method. It manages the classroom management in a dynamic teaching practice necessary to lead and provide students the role and active participation in the learning process. It improves class development, academic performance, and understanding. It increases the attitude and effectiveness of students to increase knowledge, commitment, motivation, and satisfaction in teaching and learning approach (Rivadeneira, & Inga, 2023). In addition, characteristics of faculty acts through discovery in teaching pedagogy method and concept for technological advancement in learning. It helps to motivate and discipline students to conduct, observe, inquire, and explain the natural system of learning. It recognizes advanced technology in teaching and learning process. It enhances individual learning and challenges in teaching pedagogy (Komalawardhana, & Panjaburee, 2023, pp. 1-22).

Conclusions

It shows that faculty development on instructional practices of the participants expresses expertise in the success through student learning and evaluation where it helps to improve instructional practices and teaching pedagogy for better quality education.

On the other hand, individual skills on teaching pedagogy provides individual skills to develop, lead, initiate, and plan for the subject area of student learning where it reflects individual skills for teaching learning development and critical thinking approach process.

Furthermore, knowledge on teaching pedagogy provides an insight for students to learn differently in various topics and lessons to be conducted in the learning process where it plays an important role in teaching pedagogy to help and understand the best way to provide instructional materials inside the classroom.

Notably, expertise on teaching pedagogy helps for expert interaction teaching subject didactics and learning inside the classroom where it expresses expertise in the success of development in teaching through student learning and evaluation. It also provides a pedagogical teaching practice expertise in the subject interest learning output for the academic achievement and performance of students.

Finally, characteristics of a faculty focuses on the various instructional practices and teaching pedagogy as to order of thinking skills, psychological approach to learning, and educational principles and practices where it drives for a desired output in teaching pedagogy and instructional practice output method for students to act through discovery in teaching pedagogy method and concept for technological advancement in learning.

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